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Foreigners in Italy: economic living conditions and unmet medical needs

1. INTRODUCTION

In almost all European countries, the living conditions of the foreign population are worse than those of the natives (Guio, 2005 and 2009; Lelkes, 2007; Lelkes and Zólyomi, 2011), and the situation of foreigners living in Italy follows this general trend (Istat, 2011b). In particular, immigrants in Italy experience specific barriers to health care, which can exacerbate the existing socioeconomic and geographical inequalities (Giannoni, 2010). The studies on living conditions (in terms of poverty and material deprivation) indicate that foreigners are among the most vulnerable population groups in Italy: their poverty risk is more than twice that of Italian households, and the percentage of households with foreigners who report they have difficulties making ends meet is significantly higher than that of Italian households. In addition, more than one-third of families with foreigners live in a situation of material deprivation (compared to one in seven household families with only Italians) (Istat, 2011a).

Some researchers have argued that using standard measures of poverty and/or of material deprivation is not suitable when analysing a sub-population “in transit” (Chelli and Paterno, 2002; 2006). Indeed, foreign populations have distinct consumption and saving behaviour patterns, as it is often the case that even low-income foreigners manage to save and send remittances to their family in the country of origin (Paterno, 2001; Conti *et al.*, 2003; Barsotti and Moretti, 2004). Moreover, some scholars have argued that poverty can be conceived of as being a compulsory short-term period in the life cycle that immigrants typically experience in the years immediately following their arrival (Zincone, 2000; 2001), and that they tough out while working towards a better future (Conti *et al.*, 2003).

Analyses of foreigners’ living conditions have shown that they have a greater degree of vulnerability in the labour market. While foreigners have higher labour market participation rates than Italians (Ministero dell’Interno and Istat, 2013), they also have higher rates of unemployment, especially of long-term unemployment. Moreover, foreigners are more likely than Italians to experience professional segregation, and their overall employment conditions have been worse than those of natives during the recent econom-

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ic crisis (Ministero dell'Interno and Istat, 2013). Foreigners are also more vulnerable in terms of their housing conditions (Istat, 2011a; 2011b), as they usually live in rented or sub-let accommodations, which are frequently overcrowded (Diana and Strozza, 2014).

In line with the European Commission (2013), the presence of unmet needs has been used as an indicator of inequality. This indicator points at disparities of opportunities in accessing to health care services, which may be among the drivers of social exclusion. Indeed, the European Commission (2013) has suggested that investments in sustainable health care systems would improve social cohesion by reducing health inequalities, thereby helping to break the vicious circle of poor health, poverty, and exclusion.

Empirical research has shown that immigrants are healthier than the native residents upon arrival in the destination country (“healthy immigrant effect”), but that “this initial advantage deteriorates with time spent in the host country [...] and immigrants’ health status converges toward (or below) that of native residents” (Neuman, 2014). Some scholars have attributed these trends to the underutilisation of health care services because of the lack of adequate health insurance coverage among foreigners (Antecol and Bedard, 2006). However, this explanation does not seem to apply in countries such as Italy, which has a public and universal health care system that - at least in principle - covers the whole resident population, regardless of the ability to pay and citizenship.

Despite having a health care system that is inclusive by law¹, Italy is among the European countries with a very high prevalence of unmet medical needs due to unaffordability (OECD, 2011), and foreigners in particular are likely to be unable to afford health care. The high incidence of unmet medical needs can be seen as an indicator of a low degree of socio-economic inclusion in the host country (Koolman 2007; Shaw *et al.*, 2006). For both the native and the foreign population, lack of access to health care is often associated with poverty (Chen and Hou, 2002; Cooper, 2002; Fernandes and Pereira, 2009; Koolman, 2007; Shaw *et al.*, 2006; Shi and Stevens, 2005) and poor labour market conditions (Borjas, 2000; Bollini and Siem, 1995). Moreover, inadequate knowledge of and information about national regulations can be significant obstacles to care. The literature has shown that the high rates of self-perceived unmet medical needs among the foreign population are attributable not only to detrimental economic living conditions,

¹ According to the Legislative Decree 286/1998 foreigners regularly living in Italy can register with the Italian National Health Care System (SSN - Servizio Sanitario Nazionale), and have the same access to treatment, rights, and duties as Italians (De Luca *et al.*, 2013). Foreigners who live in Italy irregularly can register as a Temporarily Present Foreigner and go to special health care centres for foreigners. It should be noted that the Temporarily Present Foreigner status can be acquired by all foreigners, regardless of their nationality or country of origin, after they complete an official form in which they declare that they have “insufficient economic resources”. Finally, asylum seekers are entitled to receive basic treatment for acute diseases free of charge.

but also to high barriers to accessing health care services (e.g., foreigners may lack knowledge about the health care system and about their rights, and have difficulties communicating with health care practitioners because of linguistic and cultural barriers).

In this context, in the current paper we seek to gain a better understanding of why some foreign national groups present a higher/lower prevalence of unmet medical needs. In particular, the aim of the paper is to investigate whether the poor economic living conditions of foreigners, which are assessed using several different measures of living conditions, influence the disparities in unmet medical needs, and whether these effects vary between foreign national groups. Moreover, after distinguishing the reasons for these disparities that are relevant from a policy perspective (i.e., those related to the unavailability or the unaffordability of health care services) from those that reflect individual heterogeneity, we investigate to what extent detrimental economic living conditions affect each of these reasons.

The paper is structured as follows: section 2 focuses on the measurement of foreigners' living conditions, section 3 describes the living conditions of the main ten nationalities by different poverty and inequality measures, and section 4 studies the relationship between economic living conditions and unmet medical needs. Section 5 summarizes the main findings and concludes.

2. A PRELIMINARY ISSUE: HOW SHOULD THE LIVING CONDITIONS OF FOREIGNERS BE MEASURED?

The general assumption that there is a strong relationship between income and standard of living may be called into question if we look at foreign sub-populations (Platt, 2007). While foreigners may derive less benefit from their income than might be expected because they are saving or remitting to family members in the country or origin, they might also be able to spend above their income using remittances received from their family in the country of origin, especially in the period immediately following migration. As Platt (2007) has emphasised, the use of income to measure poverty has the advantage that both the conceptualisation and the measurement of income are relatively straightforward. Income-based poverty measurement has several other advantages, including that it is clear what is being measured, that it does not require information about how people spend their money, and that it is not based on expectations that people should spend it in a particular way. Moreover, the choice of such a measure overcomes the problem of the definition of "essentials", which may be particularly unclear among foreigners of different nationalities (Platt 2007). Nonetheless, using an income-based poverty measure can lead to problems that may be difficult to resolve, such as whether a national or a specific poverty line for foreigners of each nationality should be used (Chelli and Paterno, 2002), whether an equiva-

lence scale that adjusts for foreigners' households should be employed (Rimoldi, Barbiano di Belgiojoso, 2014), and whether the assumption that income is shared equally within the foreigners' households applies (Platt, 2007).

Considering that the concept to be measured is the standard of living, an alternative approach is to measure standard of living directly, and thus to examine the extent to which particular groups of foreign nationals are deprived (Platt, 2007). But this choice raises questions about which items are considered "essential" for each group, and which aspects of life should be measured to ascertain whether people are deprived (for a wider discussion of deprivation measures for foreigners, see Busetta *et al.*, 2016).

Another alternative measure of standard of living focuses on the consequences of insufficient income, and, in particular, on how people feel about their finances, and whether they have difficulties making ends meet. Even if feelings of financial stress or worry are not necessarily closely related to income, this measure can provide an additional perspective on the experience of poverty and its potential consequences (Platt, 2007).

For the sake of completeness, the next sections show, discuss, and compare all these classical measures. But regardless of the measurement of poverty used, the literature indicates that the living conditions of foreigners vary considerably across Italy. Consistent with the north-south economic divide in Italy, foreigners who live in southern areas have much higher rates of poverty than those who live in northern areas. As Platt (2007) argued based on her analysis of the UK, although the economic situation of an area is independent of the presence of foreigners, the concentration of a certain group of foreigners in a less developed area implies that the group members are at increased risk of poverty.

Moreover, while it is clear that in most countries foreigners have higher rates poverty than the native-born population (regardless of how poverty is measured), there are differences in poverty levels between and within groups of foreign nationals (Platt, 2011; 2007). Both heterogeneity between groups and heterogeneity within groups are relevant when examining poverty among foreigners. Even though they are conceptually distinct, poverty and inequality are sometimes conflated (Platt, 2006). While high rates of inequality are often accompanied by high rates of poverty, this is not always the case. Looking at heterogeneity between foreigners and natives and between groups of foreigners tells us about relative disadvantage and inequalities within a society. The study of this heterogeneity helps us to understand the factors associated with a particular ethnic group that lead to greater or lesser poverty. Examining heterogeneity within groups can enable us to identify the gaps and determine their causes, and can thus inform policy strategies for mitigating inequality among foreigners. If a high level of inequality is found, there may be a need to focus on the situations of particular groups of foreigners. In the context of this study, high levels of inequality among certain groups of foreigners may be associated with barriers to accessing health care services, and thus to a high incidence of unmet health needs.

3. DATA AND DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

Our analysis examines the effects of economic living conditions on self-reported unmet medical needs. The unmet medical need indicator is included in the Italian Special Survey on Income and Living Conditions (IT-SILC) carried out by Istat in 2009 on a sample of 6,000 households with at least one foreign member drawn from the Italian Municipal Population registers. The survey was designed to reflect the distribution of foreigners by citizenship. In particular, it took into account the size of the 13 main foreign national groups (replacing non-respondents with other foreigners of the same nationality) and their geographical distribution in Italy (thereby reducing the risk of excluding national groups who are particularly concentrated in a single region of the country). Thus, the survey results allow for the analysis of the 13 main citizenships. The most numerous national groups were Romanian (about 21% of the sample), Albanian (11%), Moroccan (10%), Ukrainian (5%), Chinese (4%), Filipino (3%), Polish (3%), Moldavian (3%), Tunisian (3%), Indian (2%), Macedonian (2%), Peruvian (2%), and Ecuadorian (2%). We analyse the remaining foreign nationals in the groups other EU nationals (11%) and non-EU nationals (20%). Like the EU-SILC², this survey contains a brief health module that asks questions on self-perceived health status and self-reported unmet health care needs by reason. An individual is considered to have unmet medical needs if he/she reported having an “unmet need for medical examination or treatment” during the last 12 months³. We excluded those individuals who declared that “there was no occasion when the person really needed examination or treatment”. According to this definition, 8.6% of the foreigners surveyed had unmet medical needs⁴. However, the share of respondents who reported having unmet medical needs varied considerably by nationality group, from 3.0% among Filipinos to 14.0% among Macedonians (see percentages next to nationality labels in Figure 1).

The respondents who replied affirmatively to the self-reported unmet medical needs question were asked to identify the main reason why they had unmet medical needs. We assigned these reasons to one of three categories: affordability, availability, and other reasons⁵. The analysis of the accessibility of health services for the foreign population is complex and involves a multitude

² Note that this survey is based on the same questionnaires, survey techniques, methods of correction, imputation and integration of data, etc. of the standard EU-SILC survey, so that it is completely comparable with that of households made up exclusively of Italians obtained from the standard 2009 EU-SILC survey.

³ In particular, the question was: “During the last 12 months, was there ever a time when you felt you needed a medical examination or treatment for a health problem but you did not receive it?” Note that the choice to use the subjective assessment of unmet needs is based on the idea that the individual is the best judge of his/her health status and of whether he/she has received appropriate health care.

⁴ All of the descriptives of the IT-SILC survey of foreigners are weighted.

of factors that relate to both the health care system and the patients themselves. Indeed, low levels of access to health care services can be attributable to barriers that are specific to foreigners (e.g., a lack of knowledge about the health care system, poor knowledge of their own rights, and difficulty in communicating with health practitioners because of linguistic and cultural barriers) or simply to personal reasons (e.g., fear of doctor/treatment, the willingness to wait and see if the problem gets better without treatment, and difficulties taking the time to see a doctor because of work or childcare commitments). Moreover, beyond this general framework there are large differences between the nationality groups⁶ (see Figure 1), with relatively few Filipinos (only 22.9%) but a large share of Macedonians (83.4%) reporting that they have had problems with affordability.

Figure 1 – Main reasons for not getting a medical examination or treatment by foreigners' nationality (percentage values; Italy 2009)

Notes: Weighted sample used. Multiple responses were not allowed. Values in brackets refer to the percentage of individuals who reported having unmet medical needs.

Source: Own elaborations on Istat (2009), Italian Special Survey of Income and Living Conditions.

⁵ *Affordability* includes the answer “could not afford to”, *Availability* includes “too long waiting lists” and “too far to travel/no means of transportation” and *Other reasons* includes “Could not take time because of work, care for children etc”, “Fear of doctor/treatment”, “Wanted to wait and see if the problem got better on its own”, “Did not know any good doctor or specialist” and “Other reasons”. In the survey 61.6% of the respondents cited affordability, 12.2% cited availability, and 26.2% selected other reasons.

⁶ Please note due to the follow-up nature of this question, it only regards around 700 foreigners out of more than 8,100.

In light of the debate on the appropriateness of applying standard poverty measure to foreigners, we have chosen to use four different measures: 1) subjective poverty, 2) Eurostat's "at risk of poverty" indicator⁷, 3) material deprivation⁸, and 4) severe material deprivation⁹. Our decision to use and compare different approaches was based on widely recognised evidence that poverty is a multidimensional phenomenon that encompasses both the individual's and the household's standard of living. This is particularly the case for foreign populations, as different groups follow different models of consumption and saving, and have very different types of family households.

According to the findings for the at risk of poverty measure (Table 1), the highest level of poverty was among Ukrainians (with nearly two out of three in poverty), and the lowest level was among Peruvians (with almost one out of three in poverty). A completely different pattern emerges when we look at the results for the material deprivation measure: the highest levels of material deprivation were among Moroccans and Tunisians, while the lowest levels were among foreigners from other EU countries. The analysis of the feelings of financial stress or worry provided evidence that a large share of foreigners have difficulties making ends meet. More than 60% of Moroccans and Ecuadorians, but just 38-39% of Ukrainians, Poles, and Romanians, reported having high levels of financial distress. The inconsistent pattern that results from the four different measures is partially

⁷ The Eurostat "at risk of poverty" indicator refers to the proportion of foreigners living in a household whose total equivalised income is below 60% of the median national equivalised household income (the equivalence scale is the so-called OECD modified scale) (Guio, 2009). Comparison across groups requires a point of reference to which a comparison can be made; here we define foreigners being "at risk of poverty" relative to the Italian poverty line. Although there are risks in such an approach of "normalising" the experience of the majority, it is hard to avoid and is standard among much of the international literature (Platt 2007). Some authors (Chelli and Paterno, 2002) have argued that the overall poverty line is quite high compared to the income distribution of foreigners, and that there are two income distributions: that of natives and that of foreigners. For this reason, they identify an endogenous poverty line that more effectively describes the distribution of income among the foreign population.

⁸ According to the Eurostat definition "material deprivation" (Guio, 2009) refers to the proportion of foreigners who report that they lack at least three out of nine "enforced" essentials of life. The nine "essentials" defined by Eurostat are the ability to: 1) handle unexpected expenses; 2) afford a one-week annual holiday away from home; 3) to pay for arrears; 4) to afford a meal with meat, chicken, or fish every second day; 5) to keep their home adequately warm; and to afford 6) a washing machine, 7) a color TV, 8) a telephone, and 9) a personal car. All of the items above are available in the IT-SILC survey on foreigners. For a wider discussion on material deprivation measures among Italians and foreigners, see also Busetta *et al.* (2016).

⁹ The share of foreigners who suffer from "severe material deprivation" refers to the proportion of foreigners who report that they lack four out of the nine essentials (Guio, 2009).

due to the high degree of segmentation and labour market segregation of some nationality groups (Barbiano di Belgiojoso and Ortensi, 2015). For example, some foreigners who are employed as caregivers for the elderly (e.g., women from Ukraine, Poland, and Romania) live in the comfortable home of their employer, have no difficulties making ends meet, and do not experience material deprivation, despite having a low income. By contrast, some foreigners (e.g., men from Morocco and Tunisia) hold low-skilled manual jobs in agriculture, fishing, and/or construction; usually live alone; have a very low income; and experience high levels of material deprivation and subjective poverty.

Table 1 – *Poverty measures by foreign nationality in Italy in 2009*

Nationalities	Subjective poverty*	At risk of poverty	Material deprivation	Severe material deprivation
Albanian	55.5	39.1	35.5	17.9
Chinese	52.0	49.2	39.2	18.5
Ecuadorian	61.5	40.1	40.8	20.3
Filipino	47.9	38.3	42.4	15.5
Indian	46.4	46.9	49.1	25.4
Macedonian	50.9	46.4	36.1	16.1
Moldavian	47.1	53.4	22.8	16.9
Moroccan	66.9	54.9	57.4	31.9
Peruvian	52.9	32.8	30.1	18.0
Polish	38.2	44.3	31.6	19.7
Romanian	38.9	47.2	31.2	12.8
Tunisian	52.1	48.9	55.0	26.6
Ukrainian	38.9	62.6	29.2	14.5
other EU	30.9	34.4	20.4	8.0
other non-EU	59.9	46.1	44.6	22.5
TOTAL	49.6	45.6	37.7	18.5

Note: *Includes those who reported that they have (great) difficulties making ends meet.

Source: Own elaborations on Istat (2009), Italian Special Survey of Income and Living Conditions.

The measures of poverty used until this point in the analysis do not reflect the fact that the differences between nationality groups are trivial compared to the differences between the individual members of those groups (Platt, 2011). Equalising incomes between ethnic groups would do little to alter the overall spread of incomes and the high levels of income inequality in Italy. Platt (2011) has suggested that ethnic inequalities have little bearing on overall levels of inequality in a society, and that the experiences of minority ethnic groups are highly heterogeneous.

Thus, we decided to use and compare three different measures of inequality in our analysis¹⁰: 1) the Gini index, 2) the 90:10 ratio, and 3) the 75:25 ratio¹². While it may be possible to examine inequalities within and between foreigners based on nationality using dimensions of economic and living conditions other than income (e.g., deprivation), for the sake of brevity we examine income-based inequality measures only.

The findings indicate that there was a substantial degree of inequality among all groups and within groups (Figure 2). When we look at the results for the Gini index, we can see that the Ecuadorians had the lowest values (0.23), while the Poles had the highest values (0.41), with the other groups falling in between. When we look at the 90:10 ratio, we see that the Ukrainians in particular had extremely high values: i.e., the income received by individuals in the 90th percentile was 26.8 times higher than the income received by the individuals in the 10th percentile. This extreme result is attributable to the well-known problem that this ratio can be very sensitive to the individual incomes of a few individuals when the sample sizes are small (there were fewer than 500 Ukrainians in the sample). As the first and the last positions in the three indices differ, it is hard to discern any clear pattern. The findings for the 75:25 ratio exhibited a smaller degree of variability: in all the nationality groups, the income received by individuals in the 75th percentile was 1.8 to 2.7 higher than the income received those in the 25th percentile. As Platt (2011) pointed out, just because a group has a high poverty rate it does not mean that every member of that group has an equal chance of being in poverty. For example, if the overall poverty rate for Peruvians is approximately 33%, then any Peruvian individual will have a one in three chance of being poor. But this does not mean that every Peruvian has an equal chance of being poor, because the chances of being in poverty are also associated with the characteristics and the composition

¹⁰ For a deep examination of the properties of different measures of economic inequality, see Jenkins and Van Kerm (2009).

¹¹ The Gini index (Gini 1921) measures the extent to which the distribution of individuals income deviates from a perfectly equal distribution. It ranges between zero and one, with inequality increasing with an increasing index. A value of zero means there is a completely equal distribution of income (i.e., everyone has the same income) whereas a value of one refers to the extreme situation in which a single individual holds the total population income, and everyone else has none.

¹² The 90:10 ratio, i.e., the ratio between the income received by individuals on the 90th percentile of the distribution compared to those received by the 10th percentile, captures the degree of dispersal across the population, excluding only the highest and lowest incomes. Note that the 90:10 ratio does not tell us whether the remaining 80% were clustered around the median or were uniformly spread between these points, and it is quite unstable for measuring inequality across small groups (such as groups of foreigners based on nationality) (Platt, 2011). To overcome the weakness of this measure, Nandi and Platt (2010) used the more stable 75:25 ratio, i.e., the ratio between the income received by individuals in the 75th percentile of the distribution compared to the income received by individuals in the 25th percentile, which describes only the distribution of the central part of the income distribution (50% of incomes).

of the Peruvian group, and with other factors that lead to differential poverty rates across groups, which are still poorly understood. Nevertheless, the finding that - whatever the cause - the poverty rate of a particular group is above average simply indicates that the members of the group are disadvantaged by some specific factor or set of factors that are probably associated with that group (e.g., a high group-wide unemployment rate; a large average household size; a large share of minors).

Figure 2 – Earnings inequality measures by foreign nationality in Italy in 2009: (a) Gini index and (b) the 75:25 ratio and the 90:10 ratio

(a) Gini index by nationality

(b) The 75:25 ratio (on the left) and the 90:10 ratio (on the right) by foreign nationality

Source: Own elaborations on Istat (2009), Italian Special Survey of Income and Living Conditions.

Figure 3 – Relations between the “at risk of poverty” measure and some earnings inequality measures in Italy in 2009: the Gini index (a), the 75:25 ratio (b), and the 90:10 ratio (c)

(a) Scatter plot of the “at risk of poverty” measure and the Gini index

(b) Scatter plot of the “at risk of poverty” measure and the 75:25 ratio

(c) Scatter plot of the “at risk of poverty” measure and the 90:10 ratio

Source: Istat (2009) Italian Special Survey of Income and Living Conditions.

The analysis of inequality and poverty by nationality group does not show a clear association between poverty, as measured by the at risk of poverty measure, and inequality across the groups (Figure 3). These findings are similar regardless of the measure of poverty used. It should be noted that Ukrainians seem to have the worst economic and living conditions, with extremely high poverty rates associated with extremely high inequality values on both the 90:10 and the 75:25 ratios. By contrast, Peruvians, Ecuadorians, Indians, and Albanians have relatively low incidences of poverty and levels of inequality.

4. THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ECONOMIC LIVING CONDITIONS AND UNMET MEDICAL NEEDS: METHODS AND MAIN FINDINGS

As we noted above, the objective of this analysis is to determine whether the differences in unmet medical needs are affected by the economic living conditions of immigrants. Figure 4 compares the effect of these different measures of economic living conditions on the declared unmet medical needs using the Mantel-Haenszel odds ratio. It shows that, after adjusting for foreigner nationality, the effect of living conditions on unmet medical needs remained statistically significant, at 5%, within any of the strata. In particular, we find that being at risk of poverty had the smallest effect (OR=1.3) on unmet medical needs, whereas being subjectively poor had the largest effect (OR=3.2). No significant differences emerged among the 1st, 3rd, and 4th poverty indicators.

To test the sensitivity of the results to the choice of poverty measures in the same model, four models that each include one of the four poverty measures have been estimated. As was shown in section 3, foreigners are a heterogeneous group in terms of both the incidence of unmet medical needs and the reasons why they have unmet needs. Thus, we estimated i) four logit models to identify the effect of different poverty measures on unmet medical needs (Table 2), and ii) four multinomial logit models to assess the differences in the reported reasons for unmet medical needs across groups (Table 3).

In the logit models unmet medical needs is the response variable and the poverty measure is the main covariate. All of the models include a wide range of control variables, such as individual socio-demographic characteristics (sex, age and its squared, educational level, labour force status), individual need factors (self-assessed health status, having/not having chronic conditions or/and limitations in usual activities), and household characteristics (number of adults in the household and number of children in the household). Because of the geographical differences in the supply and the quality of health services, which have been exacerbated in the last two decades by the progressive decentralisation of health services to regional administrations (Cavalieri, 2013), all of the analyses include a control variable on the macro-region of residence in Italy.

In line with the general literature on unmet medical needs, we find that foreigners who were experiencing economic difficulties were also more likely to

have reported unmet medical needs. Interestingly, this result holds regardless of the measure included in the model (subjective poverty, material deprivation, and severe material deprivation), with the exception of the income poverty measure, which does not show a significant effect. This result is consistent with the findings of Chelli and Paterno (2002 and 2006), who argued that standard measures of poverty are not suitable when analysing foreigners because their patterns of consumption and saving are different from those of the native-born population.

Figure 4 – *Unmet medical needs by poverty measure (odds ratio values)*

Source: Istat (2009) Italian Special Survey of Income and Living Conditions.

As expected, we find that being in poor (or very poor) self-reported health, such as having limitations in daily activities or suffering from a chronic (long-standing) illness, was associated with a higher probability of having unmet medical health care needs.

In accordance with the literature (Chen, 2003), all four models detected a slightly positive effect of years since migration. Indeed, most studies on this topic have found that a longer length of residence in the destination country is associated with a relative worsening of an immigrant's health status and with a weakening of the barriers to health care services. It therefore appears that after an initial period of lower health care utilisation rates, foreigners' knowledge of the supply of health care and their ability to access these services improves, and that their expectations converge with those of the natives. Moreover, with time the social differences decrease in terms of perceptions of health and illness, awareness of health risks, and attitudes towards the benefits of medical treatment. Note that in order to better control for any effect of nationality on unmet medical needs, all of the models include nationality as a control variable.

Table 2 – Results of the logit models of unmet medical needs with different poverty measures (odds ratios)

	MODEL 1	MODEL 2	MODEL 3	MODEL 4
	with subjective poverty	with “at risk of poverty”*	with material deprivation	with severe material deprivation
<i>Economic living conditions</i>				
Make ends meet with difficulty	2.705***			
Poverty (with regard to natives)		1.153		
Material deprivation			2.192***	
Severe material deprivation				2.238***
<i>Demographic variables</i>				
Sex (ref. male)	1.328**	1.318**	1.341**	1.349**
Age	1.037	1.040*	1.039*	1.038
Squared age	0.9997	0.9996	0.9996	0.9997
<i>Health variables</i>				
Poor or very poor health	1.310	1.306	1.306	1.311
Chronic illness	2.188***	2.228***	2.102***	2.138***
Activity limitation	1.878***	1.897***	1.869***	1.912***
<i>Socio-economic variables</i>				
Position in the labour market (ref. employed)				
Self-employed	0.937	0.915	0.937	0.918
Unemployed	0.802	0.815	0.769*	0.757*
Inactive	0.556***	0.549***	0.556***	0.547***
<i>Highest ISCED level attained (ref. up to lower secondary education)</i>				
Secondary	0.808*	0.796*	0.829*	0.833
Post-secondary	0.897	0.845	0.915	0.903
<i>Household variables</i>				
No. of members of the household	0.917*	0.930	0.932	0.942
No. of dependent children	1.216**	1.209**	1.196**	1.211**
<i>Migration variables</i>				
Years since migration (no. of ys)	1.014*	1.015*	1.015*	1.015*
<i>Migration project (ref. temporary)</i>				
Permanent	1.047	1.048	1.068	1.052
Don't know	0.978	0.979	0.98	0.982
<i>Economic behaviours</i>				
Send remittances	1.049	1.067	1.064	1.086
Saving	1.237*	1.437***	1.201	1.268*
<i>Region (ref. Northern Italy)</i>				
Central Italy	1.147	1.125	1.089	1.104
Southern Italy	1.487***	1.463***	1.316**	1.300**
N	8,172	8,172	8,172	8,172
Pseudo R-squared	0.072	0.064	0.080	0.079

Notes: *** p-value<0.001; ** p-value<0.01; * p-value<0.05.

All the models control for nationality (Albanian, Chinese, Ecuadorian, Filipino, Indian, Macedonian, Moldavian, Moroccan, Peruvian, Polish, Romanian, Tunisian, Ukrainian, other EU countries, other non-EU countries).

Source: Istat (2009) Italian Special Survey of Income and Living Conditions.

Table 3 – Main results of the multinomial logit models (relative risk ratios, ref cat.: no unmet needs) of reason of unmet medical needs

	Affordability	Availability	Other
<i>Model 1 with subjective poverty</i>			
Make ends meet with difficulty	4.781***	2.369*	1.735*
Region (ref. Northern Italy)			
Central Italy	0.951	2.044*	1.305
Southern Italy	1.332*	2.201**	1.561*
N = 8,172 Pseudo R-squared = 0.083			
<i>Model 2 with “at risk of poverty”*</i>			
Poverty (with respect to natives)	1.297*	0.924	0.954
Region (ref. Northern Italy)			
Central Italy	0.926	2.037*	1.310
Southern Italy	1.275	2.306**	1.611*
N = 8,172 Pseudo R-squared = 0.076			
<i>Model 3 with material deprivation</i>			
Material deprivation	3.370***	1.039	1.271
Region (ref. Northern Italy)			
Central Italy	0.876	2.014*	1.283
Southern Italy	1.093	2.246**	1.522*
N = 8,172 Pseudo R-squared = 0.094			
<i>Model 4 with severe material deprivation</i>			
Severe material deprivation	2.911***	1.055	1.603*
Region (ref. Northern Italy)			
Central Italy	0.896	2.015*	1.281
Southern Italy	1.087	2.242**	1.464*
N = 8,172 Pseudo R-squared = 0.090			

Notes: *** p-value<0.001; ** p-value<0.01; * p-value<0.05.

All the models control for nationality (Albanian, Chinese, Ecuadorian, Filipino, Indian, Macedonian, Moldavian, Moroccan, Peruvian, Polish, Romanian, Tunisian, Ukrainian, other EU countries, other non-EU countries).

Source: Istat (2009) Italian Special Survey of Income and Living Conditions.

The multinomial logit model estimates the magnitude of the effect of different living conditions measures on each group of reasons (see Table 3). As expected having difficulties with economic or living conditions was associated with a high probability of having unmet medical needs due to unaffordability, but the magnitude of the effect varied considerably between the poverty measures. It is noteworthy to say that individuals who reported to make ends meet with difficulty are 4.7 times more likely to report unmet medical needs due to affordability reasons, whereas those foreigners who are “at risk of poverty” (i.e. poor with regard to the Italian poverty line) are only 1.3 times more likely. By contrast, availability reasons seem to depend more on the geographical distribution of health services. Individuals who were living in the southern regions were especially likely to have cited unavailability as

the reason why they had unmet medical needs, which confirms the presence of a strong north-south divide.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Italy appears to be among the European countries in which there are very large differences between economic groups in terms of the prevalence of unmet medical needs (OECD, 2011). This study shows that this gap is particularly pronounced among nationality groups whose differences in unmet medical needs are actually differences related to economic inequalities. The results of the analysis of the effects of living conditions on unmet health care needs indicate that comparing foreigners' income with the standard poverty line is not the best way to measure the living conditions of foreigners, and that measures of subjective poverty and material deprivation better capture their living conditions. Moreover, the findings suggest that the propensity to remit and to save are important economic behaviours, and that these factors have significant effects on unmet medical needs.

The Italian system is in theory free of charge for all individuals (including foreigners), regardless of their economic living conditions, and whether they have serious diseases. However, the results of the analyses indicate that the Italian system is ineffective in reducing inequalities in access to specialised medical care: irrespective of the choice of the living conditions measure, the poor have higher odds of having unmet health care needs.

The results of the models on the reasons for unmet medical needs confirm the assumption that economic inequalities (measured by self-assessed health) are related to affordability, and that there are large geographical disparities between the north and the south in access to health care.

In terms of the policy implications, our findings suggest that to improve the health and the social integration of immigrants, policies in Italy should be oriented towards reducing inequalities in access to health care, while focusing particularly on providing assistance to individuals who have high levels of self-perceived poverty, and on expanding the availability of services in the southern regions. The significance of our results is not limited to foreigners in the Italian context, as our findings can provide useful insights into health care access for immigrants in other European countries, which, like Italy, have witnessed increasing immigration flows in the last few decades.

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